

Fire Up the Dialogue

D2.4 FIRELOGUE TechMall

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
IA(s)	Innovation Action(s)
LoF	Lessons on Fire
LoF by Firelogue	Lessons on Fire powered by Firelogue Platform
TechMall	Technology Mall
WFRM	Wildfire risk management
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document (D2.4) presents the first version of the deliverable under the Task 2.3 Technology Market Place. Find [here](#) the link to explore LoF by Firelogue TechMall.

"Lessons on Fire - powered by Firelogue" is a platform that aims to make technologies related to Wildland Fire Risk Management (WFRM) more accessible and convenient through its TechMall. The platform serves as a central hub for registered users to gather information and create pages for fire-related technologies. Its technology mall offers a variety of fire-related technologies for the three phases of fire management.

The TechMall within "Lessons on Fire - powered by Firelogue" is committed to ensuring the quality and reliability of the fire-related technologies listed and benefit a wide audience such as scientists, industry, government bodies, and institutes This subpage offers a range of products and solutions, providing a platform for fire-related projects to showcase their innovations. Registered users are encouraged to contribute to the TechMall by sharing their expertise and ensuring the accuracy and currency of their information.

1 Introduction

Firelogue, as a CSA and EU project, brings together expertise from all around Europe when it comes to Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM). The connecting dimension of Firelogue focuses on the collection of knowledge, insights and solutions from the IAs, and the consolidation of this knowledge, such as of the technologies and derived services that will be developed by them (IAs).

Lessons on Fire – powered by Firelogue (LoF – by Firelogue) Platform aims to be a comprehensive resource for information and resources related to WFRM, including two (2) sections:

1. Networking
2. Knowledge Hub

The first section encompasses fire-related news and events, the sci-face, a match-making tool for scientists, and also includes the Communication Booster/EU Platforms. **The second section** is composed of the WFRM Platforms, Library, Case Study Map, TechMall and the WFRM Measures, all featuring technologies for the three phases of fire described in the Call (Prevention & Preparedness, Detection & Response, and Restoration & Adaptation).

This Deliverable (D2.4) outlines the detailed structure of the TechMall, representing the first version. The final version of the Deliverable will include the integrated visualisation of the TechMall, expected in Month 36. Task 2.3 and D2.4 are closely linked with Task 1.3 "Maturity assessment and mapping of WFRM related technologies," which developed a maturity assessment methodology and maps concrete WFRM related technologies of the IAs.

The next chapter describes, in more detail, the TechMall and its features.

2 Lessons on Fire powered by Firelogue: TechMall

The "Knowledge Hub" subpage of the LoF by Firelogue is a comprehensive repository of information related to the three phases of fire (to Prevention & Preparedness, Detection & Response, and Restoration & Adaptation), and management. The subpage is divided into four subcategories, each with a unique focus and content: WFRM Platforms, Library, Case Study Map, TechMall and the WFRM Measures (Figure 1), as described more detailed in D6.4.

Figure 1: Knowledge Hub page with some of the subpages

TechMalls offer customers a centralized location to compare technology products and stay current with the latest advancements. Firelogue seeks to establish an online WFRM community through its platform, featuring a display of technologies, dissemination platforms, fire-related resources, a knowledge repository, and other features where registered users can provide input.

The TechMall's inclusion as a subcategory in the "Knowledge Hub" subpage is strategic and purposeful. The importance of technology and products in the three stages of fire is significant. By showcasing and providing information on these products in a dedicated section of the platform, users can gain a comprehensive understanding of available options in the market and an insight into their impact. The TechMall serves as a valuable resource for those seeking informed decisions about technology and products for fire protection. It aligns with Firelogue's overall goal of providing comprehensive and accessible information and resources for fire protection and management.

Maturity cards

Firelogue has utilized the Maturity Assessment Methodology, conducted in Task 1.3 and described in D1.3 to enhance the TechMall. By filling the TechMall's Form and the Maturity Card (see Appendix 1), various types of users, such as technology providers and developers, provide as much information as possible to create a complete profile of their technology. After in depth research and consultation with stakeholders, Firelogue consortium concluded that the sections in the Maturity Card are the most key and insightful ones to give a comprehensive overview to the viewers about each product/technology, such as phase of fire, benefits etc.

The LoF by Firelogue restricts access upload any Maturity Cards only to registered users to ensure the accuracy and reliability of information provided. Registered users are also able to provide updates and feedback on their uploaded technologies to keep the TechMall up to date. However, although providers must be registered users, the information on the platform is open to all.

Through Maturity Cards (see Appendix 1), the registered user can upload all necessary information to assist other interested users, including scientists, industry, government bodies, and institutes, to understand the latest fire-related technologies and make informed decisions about investments, adoption, and collaboration. Maturity Cards can also help other projects and stakeholders in the fire industry to understand their technology's strengths and weaknesses, and to identify areas for improvement and avoid over lapses. Maturity Cards provide a structured way of evaluating the technology's potential and its readiness for implementation and commercialization.

It is important to note that the TechMall serves as a central repository for gathering information on various technologies, making it easier and more convenient for users to access and understand the technology. Therefore, the users who provide the information are responsible for it and are the key contacts for further communication.

Target audiences

The TechMall has identified target audiences to ensure its success. The platform is designed for professionals, organizations, and individuals involved in the fire-related industries, such as firefighting, policy makers, insurance, and fire safety. This includes a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, engineers, consultants, firefighters, safety professionals, building owners and managers, and government agencies, among others. The TechMall aims to provide a valuable resource for these groups, offering a comprehensive selection of technologies and products for fire protection and management.

These individuals and organizations would be interested in accessing information about the latest fire-related technologies to enhance their knowledge and improve fire-related practices, procedures, and operations. The TechMall serves as a platform for **researchers** and scientists to remain informed about the most recent developments in fire-related technologies. **Industry** professionals can find new investment opportunities by exploring the latest technologies in the field. **Government** bodies can use the information provided in the TechMall to make informed decisions related to fire management. **Institutes** and other fire-related **projects** can benefit not only by accessing information about technologies, but also by advertising themselves and reach a wider audience by displaying their products and services in the TechMall. Additionally, the platform's **network** of experts and resources can help facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing among organizations and individuals working in the fire-related field.

As mentioned, TechMall is designed to make the process of discovering and learning about technology related to fire protection and safety more streamlined and accessible. With its focus on

making access to technology related to WFRM easier and immediate, TechMall is a valuable resource for those seeking information and products in this area.

Timeline

The TechMall has been initially designed by Firelogue partners involved in this Task and the specification of the Platform. Major input has been provided by Task 1.2 (led by SAFE CLUSTER); Task 1.3 (led by NOA) and WP1 leaders (IIASA) that have worked together to consolidate all necessary input into a unified document format, thereby reducing the burden on IAs to complete multiple forms. The initial structure of the form has been circulated among other partners within the Firelogue consortium for review and feedback.

Subsequently, Tech-Form (see Appendix 2) was submitted to KEMEA, a partner in Firelogue, as well as SILVANUS Innovation Action, in order to solicit feedback regarding the validity and feasibility of the form. Their input significantly enhanced our analysis of the maturity level of the platform, resulting in the identification of indicators that are applicable to both the services developed by the IAs and the overall user-friendliness of the form.

The ultimate iteration of the form has been published online and is currently available for feedback solicitation. As per the guidelines laid out in D1.3, the stakeholder manager of Firelogue will initiate contact with the coordinators of the IAs, who will subsequently disseminate the relevant information among their respective consortia.

TechMall Specifications in topics

Users of TechMall should exercise caution and due diligence when utilizing the platform. The following considerations should be taken into account:

1. **Information Accuracy:** Information available on the platform is obtained directly from the technology providers to ensure accuracy.
2. **Communication Responsibility:** It is the responsibility of the user to directly communicate with providers for any inquiries or concerns. Although the information of the providers is given, LoF by Firelogue is always available for further assistance.
3. **Product Liability:** Firelogue does not assume liability for the quality or performance of products in the platform as TechMall is a place of technology display and the information is given by the technology providers.
4. **Availability of Products:** Availability of products may vary and users should confirm product availability with technology providers.
5. **Repair and Installation Services:** Availability of repair and installation services may be limited and users should confirm availability and fees with technology providers.
6. **Privacy and Security:** LoF by Firelogue provides all the necessary privacy policies based on the EU GDPR (Appendix 2).

3 Conclusion

In conclusion, the LoF by Firelogue Platform provides a valuable resource for individuals and organizations interested in the field of wildfire risk management (WFRM). The TechMall, one of the platform's key features, offers a comprehensive and up-to-date collection of fire-related technologies, which can be accessed by a variety of stakeholders.

Additionally, the platform provides opportunities for users to share their knowledge, connect with other professionals, and stay informed about the latest fire-related events and news. With its commitment to data privacy and collaboration with industry experts, Firelogue's TechMall is a valuable tool for anyone interested in addressing the pressing issue of wildfire risk management.

Find [here](#) to explore LoF by Firelogue TechMall.

4 Appendix

Appendix 1: Tech-Form & Maturity Card

Photo <i>(please upload a relevant photo)</i>			
Solution Title	<i>Please write a title</i>	Project	Choose an item.
Solution Provider	<i>Please write your organisation</i>	Case Study/Pilot area to be applied	<i>Please write where will you implement your service</i>
Description	<i>Please write a brief description of the solution</i>		
Relevant Phase	<input type="checkbox"/> Prevention and Preparedness <input type="checkbox"/> Detection and Response <input type="checkbox"/> Restoration and Adaptation		
Targeted Stakeholder(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Emergency management organizations (e.g. firefighters, civil protection; medical services and police; first responders performing operations in the field; fire analysts) <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific community e.g., research and academic institutions <input type="checkbox"/> Policy-making bodies e.g., administrations; EU commissioners; politicians <input type="checkbox"/> Land Management groups e.g., landowner associations; land planners; farmers; foresters <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental associations e.g., conservation organizations; environmental consultancies; environmental educators <input type="checkbox"/> Media e.g., journalists; communicators in the environmental field <input type="checkbox"/> Society e.g., social groups; volunteer associations; representatives for certain citizen groups; vulnerable groups <input type="checkbox"/> Industry, technology, and innovation e.g., the industry around sectors of energy, construction, infrastructures, timber, fire prevention and firefighting equipment; Banking, Financial Services, and Insurance industry		
Benefits	<i>Please write any kind of benefit (economic, societal, scientific, technological etc...) that comes from this solution</i>		
Results	<i>Please write the results of this solution and if they meet the expectations of the concept that were created</i>		
Website	<i>Please enter the website of the specific solution (alternatively enter the project's website)</i>		
Green Deal Impact relation	<i>Please refer briefly to the relation of the solution to the target impacts of the green deal for preventing wildfires</i>		

Standards' compatibility	<i>is the solution compatible with standards and which ones</i>	
Further references and resources	<i>Please write any relevant references (publications, policy briefs, handbooks etc.) to your solution (if relevant)</i>	
Maturity Indicators with regard to technological solutions only		
Capacity	Successful Years of Operation of the service <i>The degree of successful year in time shows the maturity of a service.</i>	Choose an item.
	Technology Readiness Level <i>A systematic metric system that supports assessments of the maturity of a particular technology</i>	Choose an item.
	ISO certified service <i>Services that get ISO or other quality certifications (meet specific standards) show high maturity level.</i>	Choose an item.
Uptake	Market readiness level <i>The market aspect of services' development related to a) the extent of their availability; b) their demand c) the market readiness to adopt them and d) the availability for widespread use.</i>	Choose an item.
	Number of countries and/or different organisations that adopted these services <i>If a service is adopted by more countries and/or organisations, this means that it is mature enough.</i>	Choose an item.
Funding and Economy	EU (re-)funding and investments (in times) <i>The EU has refunded multiple times the specific technology for operational goals.</i>	Choose an item.
	Government (national) Funding (in times) <i>The national Government funds the production of the service.</i>	Choose an item.
	Industry Funding (in times) <i>Industries fund the production of the service.</i>	Choose an item.
Education and Society	Universities teaching a relevant course in their study programme <i>The maturity of a service is correlated with the teaching activity of the Universities.</i>	Choose an item.
	Support policy and/or decision-makers <i>National Government trusts this solution and can be used for societal reasons.</i>	Choose an item.
	Social acceptance readiness level (SRL)	Choose an item.

	<p><i>The level of knowledge about the stakeholders' interests as well as to what extent the service affects society, starting from recognition up to stakeholders' involvement.</i></p>	
	<p>Potential side effects (positive or negative) on members of society and/or ecosystems (e.g. infrastructure changing the amenity value of a forest) <i>Societal acceptance and potential conflicting interests are important in determining the implementation of a technology, and the diffusion of the respective solution. Awareness of potential limitations is important for effective policy design.</i></p>	Choose an item.
	<p>Potential side effects (positive or negative) on other/future aspects of WFRM (e.g. changes in fuel loads or ecosystems) <i>Societal acceptance and potential conflicting interests are important in determining the implementation of a technology, and the diffusion of the respective solution. Awareness of potential limitations is important for effective policy design.</i></p>	Choose an item.

Appendix 2: Privacy Policy

Privacy Policy

lessonsonfire.firelogue.eu

Firelogue is an EU Coordination and Support Action (CSA), which connects the three EU Innovation Actions (IAs) granted under the H2020-LC-GD-1-1-2020 call and supports them by integrating their findings across various stakeholders' groups and phases of Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM). Firelogue develops a platform that aims to promote dialogue between different actors across Europe's wildlife communities.

All Firelogue partners are committed to the protection of your personal data. Therefore, we take the necessary and proportionate measures to protect, secure and maintain the integrity and availability of your data processed via the Platform lessonsonfire.firelogue.eu ("Platform").

Users are encouraged to read this Privacy Policy carefully. By using the Platform you have read and understood the terms of this privacy policy. If you do not agree to these terms, you should not use the Platform. Using the Platform after modifications to this Privacy Policy constitutes your understanding of those changes.

The Privacy Notice is directly linked to and accompanies the Terms of Use of the Platform. Please refer to them for more information.

Data Controller

The Partners under the name "**EDGE IN EARTH OBSERVATION SCIENCES**" ("EDGE") ,with corporate seat at 36 1b Smirnis Street, Zografou, 15772, Athens, Greece, and "**Fundació d'Ecologia del Foc i Gestió d'Incendis Pau Costa Alcubierre -PAU COSTA FOUNDATION**" ("PCF"), with corporate seat at Av. Mossèn Cinto Verdaguer, 42 esc. A bxs 2A, 08552 Taradell Barcelona,Spain are the administrators of the Platform and Joint Data Controller for the personal data processed via the platform and for the Services it offers.

You may can contact the Partners for any request regarding your data by sending an email to info@firelogue.eu.

Data we collect from you

The Platform has an informative character and aims to promote dialogue. Thus, you may participate by creating a User account, share publications, upload content and also you may contact the Platform to send a message and/or to express your interest in becoming a member the network.

In such cases Users may accordingly be requested to provide:

Identification Data	First Name Last Name Photo (optional)
Communication data	Email Country (optional)
Other Personal Information	Gender (optional) CV/ Job Profile (optional) Topics of interest (optional)
Company details	Organization (optional)

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By subscribing to the newsletter and its receipt, the following personal data of users are collected:

Communication Data	Email
Personal Information	IP address

Data we collect by automated means

When you use our Platform your device automatically provides us with data so that we can serve and tailor our response to you. The type of information we collect through automated means generally includes technical information about your device, such as the IP address or other device ID, the type of device you are using, and the version of the operating system.

The data we collect may also include usage information and statistics about your interaction with the Platform

We encourage you to read our Cookies Policy carefully to learn more about Cookies, how to use them and how you can control their use.

Purpose & Lawful Basis for personal data processing

The processing of personal data of users is subject to the terms hereof, the relevant provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (EU / 2016/679), and all applicable data protection and privacy legislation in force from time to time in the EU including the Privacy and Electronic Communications Directive 2002/58/EC (as updated by Directive 2009/136/EC) and as implemented in the member states of reference; and any other European Union legislation relating to Personal Data and the guidelines and decisions of the European Data Protection Supervisor, of the European Data Protection Board and of the Supervisory Authorities.

We use data we collect through our Platform for the following purposes and based on the following lawful bases:

- Purpose: To create a user profile and to share your personal data in the directory for networking purposes
Lawful basis: Consent
- Purpose: Communication with users upon request
Lawful basis: Legitimate interest of the company to answer to messages and provide for networking
- Purpose: To create a knowledge database and enhance wildfire risk management
Lawful basis: Archiving for the public interest
- Purpose: News updates & platform promotion by subscribing to the newsletter
Lawful basis: Consent

We may also process and forward user personal data to comply with our legal obligations or orders from the relevant police, public and judicial authorities.

Data Retention

In case a User has become a member of the Firelogue community by creating an account, we retain its data until it requests its deletion or in any way revokes its consent. Any other data are retained until Users remove it themselves.

User data collected for sending newsletters with their consent is also retained until the user revokes its consent and is deleted from the service, either by changing the corresponding settings on their device, or by using the unsubscribe option provided in relevant communications.

For the duration of the retention of the information collected through cookies, please be informed by the Cookies Policy.

Recipients of data

Your data may need to become available to EDGE's and PCF's personnel, and website maintenance technicians (Notsoda). All parties are bound by the obligation of confidentiality and due process.

The Platform is hosted in private servers of PCF within the EU and we do not transfer your data to third parties. Notsoda operates as data processors and are bound by the obligation of compliance with the rules of confidentiality and lawful processing as provided in the relevant data protection legislation.

Please note that your personal data may be disclosed (i) to partners of the consortium for operational reasons based on our legitimate interest on a strict need to know basis, or (ii) in any case where we are required to do so under applicable law or when necessary for the purposes of our legal interests protection, always ensuring that the guarantees for its safety and protection is met.

Contact the Platform

The communication with our Platform is available via email at info@firelogue.eu.

Only our authorized personnel, who is bound by confidentiality clauses or by a regulatory obligation of confidentiality, have access to the messages we receive on our platform.

We do not forward messages to third parties which we receive on our platform without the explicit consent of the sender.

Exceptions to the above, are cases in which forwarding to third parties or not deleting the emails we receive, is necessary to comply with our obligations arising from the law or to establish, exercise or support legal claims.

Technical Measures of the Platform

We work with the Platform's hosting service provider, to ensure that your personal data is protected, maintaining the data of our website within the European Economic Area. Data is protected by European legislation.

Our Platform uses an encryption system (SSL) to ensure greater security during your navigation.

We might use third party vendors and hosting partners to provide the necessary hardware, software, storage and related technology required for the operation of the Platform. We may store encrypted backups of our database to a third-party storage provider to ensure its security in the event of an emergency or disaster.

Social Media

Firelogue uses social media to promote its Services. This policy does not apply when you use social media to get in touch with our Platform. Instead, the processing of your personal data is subject to the privacy policy of such social media. We advise you to read the social media privacy policy carefully before using them.

Your Rights

You have the following rights regarding your personal data	
Right to information	You have the right to be informed about the collection and processing of your personal data
Right to access	You have the right to receive confirmation from us as to whether or not your personal data is being processed and, if so, you have the right to access your personal data in a concise, comprehensible, transparent and easily accessible form.
Right to correction	You can request and we will ensure that without undue delay we will correct inaccurate or incomplete personal data, including via a supplementary statement.
Right to erasure	You have the right to ask us to delete the personal data that concern you, without undue delay and we will proceed with the deletion, under the conditions set by the law.
Right to processing limitation	You have the right to ask us to limit processing activities to specific purposes only, subject to the conditions set by the law.
Right to object	You have the right to object, at any time and for reasons related to your particular situation, to the processing of personal data concerning you. We will no longer process personal data unless there are compelling and legitimate reasons for processing that override your interests, rights and freedoms or to establish, exercise or uphold legal claims.
Right to data portability	You have the right to receive the personal data concerning you, which you have provided us with, in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format, as well as the right to request the transfer of such data to another processor without objection from us under the conditions set by the law.
Right to human interference	You have the right to not be subject to a decision made solely on the basis of automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects that concern you or significantly affect you in a similar way.

If you have any questions about this privacy notice or would like to ask for clarification or if you wish to exercise any of your rights or withdraw your consent to any communication, please contact info@firelogue.eu

We will respond to your request within thirty (30) days of receipt. In the event that an extension of the above deadline is required for the investigation and / or processing of your request, we will inform you, explaining the reasons why the extension of the deadline is necessary.

In any case, if you feel that the protection of your personal data has been violated in any way, you have the right to file a complaint to either the Hellenic Personal Data Protection Authority (www.dpa.gr) or the Spanish Personal Data Protection Authority ([www. sedeagpd.gob.es](http://www.sedeagpd.gob.es)). For the Authorities' jurisdiction and the way of submitting a complaint, you can visit their website where there is detailed information.

Modification of this Privacy Policy

We may make changes to this Policy from time to time. We may make these modifications for a variety of reasons, for example to reflect changes or requirements arising from the law, new features or changes in corporate practices. The latest version will be published in the relevant place on the Platform. You should check often to find the latest version. The latest version is the applicable one. If the changes involve significant ones that affect your rights or obligations, we will notify you in advance via reasonable means, which may include notice through the Platform or by email. If you continue to use the Services after the changes take effect, you agree to the revised notice.

THIS IS THE END OF THIS DOCUMENT

